

Entropy: as momentum in thermodynamics

Kapil P. Chandra*

Abstract

We found that entropy and space are interrelated via the Heisenberg uncertainty relation. However, we make the simple argument that entropy is analogous to the momentum of mechanics. It means to say that entropy works as momentum in thermodynamics. It describes its new role in thermodynamics.

1 Introduction

Entropy is one of the least understood concepts in physics, but basically, it's a thermodynamical physical entity [1] [2] [3]. There is no physical analogy [4]. Although it is defined as randomness, disorder, or uncertainty. It is a measurable physical entity, but there is no direct method to measure it [5] [6] [7]. Thermodynamically, it is a form of energy; however, it is related to energy by the following relations: Thermodynamically, it is a form of energy; however, it is related to energy by the following relations:

$$\nabla E = T \nabla S \quad (1)$$

where E is energy of the system; T , S is temperature and entropy respectively.

Cassius described entropy as a physical entity and energy of the thermodynamic system that is unavailable to execute work [8]. In his terms, if we increase the heat or temperature of the system, execution of work is not possible, so the added heat will only increase the entropy of the system. It's an internal property of a thermodynamic system, and the temperature and entropy are dynamical variables.

*kapil.chandra@gov.in

2 Relation between entropy and space

If we take $E = \frac{hc}{\nabla x}$ in the context of entropic force, where it is denoted as $F \nabla x = T \nabla S$, then Eq. (1) will turn into the following:

$$\nabla_s \nabla x = \frac{hc}{T} \quad (2)$$

this shows the relation between the space and entropy of a system in terms of the Planck constant; it's actually shows the dynamic relation between both entity.

3 Analogy between entropy and momentum

The Eq. (2) is analogous to the Heisenberg uncertainty relation [9] at constant temperature, therefore, we can rewrite it as follows,

$$\nabla_s \nabla x \geq \frac{hc}{T} \quad (3)$$

here, one can observe that entropy is just analogous to momentum, and thus we infer that entropy in thermodynamics is similar to the momentum of mechanics. This suggests that the same role is played by momentum in quantum

physics as it is by entropy in thermodynamics. This might be promising to understand and describe the entropy in different point of view and may give new direction of study since momentum is most important physical entity in mechanics.

This work leads us to make an analogy between the law of thermodynamics and Newton's law of motion. As we have shown, entropy and momentum correspond to each other, and both are basic ingredients of the second law in both theories. This is an incredible similarity. However, one can make an analogy between the law of thermodynamics and the law of motion in a loose sense. This will help to interconnect and elaborate mechanics and thermodynamics.

4 Conclusions

Entropy is analogous to momentum. However, entropy follows the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, and there is an uncertainty relation between entropy and space for an isolated thermodynamical system. This is a new set of uncertainty relations in physics and gives a new interpretation of entropy. Apart to it, it may help to make analogy between the law of thermodynamics and Newton's law of motion and breaks a new ground of research.

Acknowledgements: I would like to say thanks to Dr HS for his comment on the manuscript to make it better.

References

- [1] Constantino Tsallis. Entropy. *Encyclopedia*, 2(1):264–300, 2022. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-8392/2/1/18>, doi: 10.3390/encyclopedia2010018.
- [2] J Willard Gibbs. The collected works of j. willard gibbs. Technical report, Yale Univ. Press,, 1948.
- [3] Daniel R Brooks, Edward O Wiley, and DR Brooks. *Evolution as entropy*. University of Chicago Press Chicago, 1988.
- [4] Berthold Bein. Entropy. *Best Practice Research Clinical Anaesthesiology*, 20(1):101–109, 2006. Monitoring Consciousness. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1521689605000558>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2005.07.009>.
- [5] A. Bialas and W. Czyz. Measurement of entropy of a multiparticle system: a do-list, 2000. arXiv:hep-ph/0002140.
- [6] Mauricio S. Ribeiro, Gabriela A. Casas, and Fernando D. Nobre. Second law and entropy production in a nonextensive system. *Phys. Rev. E*, 91:012140, Jan 2015. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevE.91.012140>, doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.91.012140.
- [7] Jayadev Acharya, Ibrahim Issa, Nirmal V. Shende, and Aaron B. Wagner. Measuring quantum entropy. In *2019 IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory (ISIT)*, pages 3012–3016, 2019. doi: 10.1109/ISIT.2019.8849572.
- [8] R. Clausius. Ueber verschiedene für die anwendung bequeme formen der hauptgleichungen der mechanischen wärmetheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 201(7):353–400, 1865. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/andp.18652010702>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/andp.18652010702>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.18652010702>.
- [9] annotated by A. Angelow and M. C. Batoni. About heisenberg uncertainty relation (by e.schrodinger). 1999. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/9903100>, doi:10.48550/ARXIV.QUANT-PH/9903100.